

ON SOME SERIES INVOLVING
SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

by

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The study of infinite series involving Smarandache function is one of the most interesting aspects of analysis.

In this brief article we give only a bare introduction to it.

First we prove that the series $\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(kH)!}$ converges and has the sum $\sigma \in \left] e^{-\frac{5}{2}}, \frac{1}{2} \right[$.

$S(m)$ is the Smarandache function: $S(m) = \min \{k \in \mathbf{N}; m | k!\}$.

Let us denote $1 + \frac{1}{1!} + \frac{1}{2!} + \dots + \frac{1}{n!}$ by E_n . We show that

$$E_{n+1} - \frac{5}{2} < \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!} < \frac{1}{2} \text{ as follows:}$$

$$\sum_{k=2}^n \frac{k}{(k+1)!} = \sum_{k=2}^n \left(\frac{1}{k!} - \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \right) = \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{1}{k!} - \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{1}{(k+1)!} = \frac{1}{2!} - \frac{1}{(n+1)!}$$

$$S(k) \leq k \text{ implies that } \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!} \leq \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{k}{(k+1)!} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{(k+1)!} < \frac{1}{2}.$$

On the other hand $k \geq 2$ implies that $S(k) > 1$ and consequently:

$$\sum_{k=2}^n \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!} > \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{1}{(k+1)!} = \frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \dots + \frac{1}{n+1!} = E_{n+1} - \frac{5}{2}.$$

It follows that $E_{n+1} - \frac{5}{2} < \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!} < \frac{1}{2}$ and therefore

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!} \text{ is a convergent series with sum } \sigma \in \left[e - \frac{5}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right].$$

REMARK: Some of inequalities $S(k) \leq k$ are strictly and $k \geq S(k) + 1$, $S(k) \geq 2$. Hence $\sigma \in \left[e - \frac{5}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right]$.

We can also check that $\sum_{k=r}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k-r)!}$, $r \in \mathbb{N}^*$ and $\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+r)!}$, $r \in \mathbb{N}$,

are both convergent as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=r}^n \frac{S(k)}{(k-r)!} &\leq \sum_{k=r}^n \frac{k}{(k-r)!} = \frac{r}{0!} + \frac{r+1}{1!} + \frac{r+2}{2!} + \dots + \frac{r+(n-r)}{(n-r)!} = \\ &= r \left(\frac{1}{0!} + \frac{1}{1!} + \dots + \frac{1}{(n-r)!} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{1!} + \frac{2}{2!} + \dots + \frac{n-r}{(n-r)!} \right) = rE_{n-r} + E_{n-r-1} \end{aligned}$$

We get $\sum_{k=r}^n \frac{S(k)}{(k-r)!} < rE_{n-r} + E_{n-r-1}$ which that $\sum_{k=r}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k-r)!}$

converges.

Also we have $\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+r)!} < \infty$, $r \in \mathbb{N}$.

Let us define the set $M_2 = \left\{ m \in \mathbb{N} : m = \frac{n!}{2}, n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 3 \right\}$.

If $m \in M_2$ it is obvious that

$$S(m) = n, \quad m = \frac{n!}{2}, \quad m \in M_2 \rightarrow \frac{m}{S(m)!} = \frac{n!}{2}.$$

So, $\sum_{\substack{m=3 \\ m \in M_2}}^{\infty} \frac{m}{S(m)!} = \infty$ and therefore $\sum_{\substack{k=2 \\ k \in \mathbb{N}}}^{\infty} \frac{k}{S(k)!} = \infty$.

A problem: test the convergence behaviour of the series

$$\sum_{\substack{k=2 \\ k \in \mathbb{N}}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(k)!}.$$

REFERENCES

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